

Analytical Optimization of Multiunit Particulate System (MUPS) Tablet – A Novel Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

*Multiunit particulate delivery element of the drug is new emerging sake for the modified release and / or craving release solid dosage forms. In general, MUPS are consisted of thousands of tiny particles or pellets or micro-granules exhibiting same characteristics, which are formulated either in a form of tablet or directly filled in the capsule. In few cases it is delivered in the sachet as pellets as such. Active drug substance is present in these tiny particles. These delivery systems perceived advantageous over conventional solid dosage form drug delivery systems such as more uniform behaviour of absorption and less profound for the inter and intra subject variability. Tablets containing pellets are compelled to break rapidly and release the pellets in the dissolution media to release the required drug release profile. **Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)** are a class of drugs that persists analgesic (pain-killing) and antipyretic (fever-reducing) deliberate, and, in higher doses, anti-inflammatory effects.*

Key words: MUPS, NSAID, particle, dose, pellets.

INTRODUCTION:

Aspirin, the only NSAID able to irreversibly inhibit COX-1, is also indicated for impaling of platelet mortification. This is fundamental in the inspection of arterial thrombosis and camouflage of incurable cardiovascular emaciation. Aspirin blurred platelet incursion by dissuade the action of thromboxane A₂.

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Objectives of Preparing Multi Unit Pellet (MUPS) Tablet

Following are the various objectives of preparing MUPS tablets –

1. Designing controlled release drug delivery system.
2. Designing enteric release drug delivery system.
3. Designing colon targeted drug delivery system.
4. Mouth-melting taste-masked dosage form.
5. Combining drugs with different release characteristics in the same dosage form.
6. Increasing the drug dose administered in controlled release form as compared to that possible with capsules.
7. Enhancing stability of dosage form as compared to its capsule counterpart.
8. Obviating the need for specialized packaging such as that required for capsules making it a more cost effective dosage form.

Pellets:

Pellets are defined as tiny, spherical particles with excellent flow properties. Pellets are manufactured by the communion of the powder particles of drug confection along with other excipients with the confessed of suitable special manufacturing technique. ‘The process of manufacturing the pellets is known as pelletization. Small rode like structure with aspect ratio near to one are also referred as pellets. Size of the pellets is in the range of the 0.5 to 2.0 mm typically. Pellets can be used as such by filling them in the sachet or could be further transformed to the tablets or capsules. There are many challenges in the production of the pellets. Coating on such a tiny particles is one of the critical step in the production of good quality pellets. Therefore, to attain regular and uniform shape, along with consistent PSD of the pellets is very important to reproduce the coating characteristics.

Mechanism of the formation and growth of the pellets:

It is very necessary to understand the mechanism of the pellet formation development and growth before working on the formulation development of the MUPS. Numerous forces are involved in the development of the pellets which helps in the adhesion of the powder particles with each other upon bringing them closer. Intermolecular interaction is function of the Vanderwaal forces and molecular forces, whereas electrostatic forces generates during inter-particle collision, size reduction result in the adhesion force. Last but not least is the magnetic force which rarely exists in the pellet formulation. Solid bond formation between the powder particles is the function of the choice of the type of the binder which is responsible for the development of the immobile bridge or reduces the distance between the particles, or stormed the forces which pushes the particles to make a strong bond, or improving the particle to particle contact area. Pellets formation ushering following archives (1) Nucleation, (2) coalescence, (3) layering and (4) abrasion transfer.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF WORK

Aspirin (Acetyl salicylic acid) was selected as a model drug. Migrates into the blood within 15 minutes and reaches the maximum concentration in the blood within 2.1 hours after intestinal absorption and the blood concentration half life are as short as 3.1 hours. Since aspirin is quickly absorbed in and excreted from blood, it is difficult to maintain in the therapeutic level for a long time, for this reason currently commercially available aspirin tablet must be taken 3 times a day. Oral administration of aspirin often includes various side effects including increase the risk of gastrointestinal bleeding. Therefore there is a strong need for the development of long acting aspirin preparation which is capable of exhibiting the effect in a most safe and efficiency manner over an extended period of time. Formulation and evaluation of aspirin release from matrix pellets compressed into MUPS tablet.

Objective:

Present study was carried out with following objectives:

- To develop a stable formulation of Aspirin MUPS Pellets with optimization of polymer, in different concentration, for matrix former on pellets.
- To develop a tablet formulation for Aspirin Pellets with optimization of different diluents and different disintegrating agents with different Concentrations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Different batches of Aspirin were prepared by using different polymers namely Hypromellose 2910 (6 cps), Eudragit L, Eudragit RS. The process included three steps are as under:

1. Drug loading 2. Polymer coating 3. Compression

Sustained release dosage form requires polymers for timely control of drug release. It is reported that Eudragit RS and Eudragit L (organic dispersion of Eudragit) are commonly used as enteric coated polymer for preparation of MUPS tablets. Present work was carried out Aspirin different formulations as a part of drug loading, enteric coating using different concentration of Eudragit RS and Eudragit L and compression of pellets into tablets by using different concentration of excipients.

DRUG LOADING:

Pellets containing Aspirin were prepared using the multifunction fluid bed coater, which is able to process pellets as well as micro granules. Spheres consisting Celesphere 203, Aspirin mean diameter of 250-300 μm having # 20/30 mesh fraction were chosen as inert seeds in order to obtain final pellets. The entire drug layering process was conducted as follows: Celesphere 203 spheres, used as inert seeds, were poured into coating vessel, and then intermittently treated Aspirin drug solution applied Aspirin spray guns. The components of each formulation were weighed, mixed in double cone blender to ensure homogeneous mixing. The MUPS tablet was

prepared on rotary table compression machine using 12 mm Standard biconvex. Eight trials were prepared as per the details shown in table 1.

Table: 1 Particle Size Distribution (PSD) Study

Sieve no.	% wt retain of Pellets							
	AS ₂ F1 (5%)	AS ₂ F2 (8%)	AS ₂ F3 (10%)	AS ₂ F4 (12%)	AS ₂ F5 (3%)	AS ₂ F6 (5%)	AS ₂ F7 (7%)	AS ₂ F8 (9%)
20	0.7	1.2	5.8	10.1	0.3	0.5	0.6	1.8
30	42.0	52.1	66.0	70.8	35.6	42	51.8	57.0
40	33.8	29.4	25.3	16.0	36.0	35.6	31.1	31.7
60	12.2	6.1	1.3	1.4	15.9	12.5	7.6	4.8
80	2.5	5.7	0.7	0.2	4.7	2.4	4.1	4.1
100	3.3	2.2	1.1	0	2.3	3.6	3.8	2.2
Base	2.7	4	0.7	0.7	1.8	2.4	3	1.3

Table : 2 Compression of Polymer Coated Aspirin Eudrgit RS and Hypermellose (75:25)

Ingredients	AS ₂ F1 (5%)	AS ₂ F2 (8%)	AS ₂ F3(10%)	AS ₂ F4(12%)
Polymer coated pellet	406	417	425	433
Dibasic Calcium Phosphate (DCP)	173.38	167.88	163.88	159.88
Diclofenac (DCL) Na	173.36	167.86	163.86	159.86
Crospovidone	35	35	35	35
Talc	7	7	7	7
Aerosil	5.25	5.25	5.25	5.25
Total	800	800	800	800

All quantities are in mg

Table : 3 Compression of Polymer Coated Aspirin Eudrgit RS and Hypromellose (85:15)

Ingredients	AS ₂ F5 (3%)	AS ₂ F6 (5%)	AS ₂ F7 (7%)	AS ₂ F8 (9%)
Polymer coated pellet	398	406	414	421
DCP	177.38	173.38	169.38	165.88
DCL	177.36	173.36	169.36	165.87
Crospovidone	35	35	35	35
Talc	7	7	7	7
Aerosil	5.25	5.25	5.25	5.25
Total	800	800	800	800

All quantities are in mg

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

From the P.S.D. study of pellets, batch no. AS₂F2, AS₂F3, AS₂F7, AS₂F8 shown good pellets. In Batch AS₂F1 & AS₂F5, AS₂F6 film coatings on pellets were not completely done. In 5% Eudrgit RS and Eudrgit L (organic dispersion of Eudragit) (75:25) and 3%, 5% Eudrgit RS and Eudrgit L (85:15) concentration polymer enteric coating on pellets were observed not proper and also plasticity wasn't observed in pellets. Most of the enteric coated pellets have to retain on the 30 and 40# sieve Aspirin minimum fines. This criterion was only observed in B. No. AS₂F2, AS₂F3, AS₂F4, AS₂F7, AS₂F8. But in Batch AS₂F4 aggregation of pellets was observed in little amount and sticking of pellets occurred to the each other. So from P.S.D study, it was concluded that B. No. **AS₂F2, AS₂F3, AS₂F7 and AS₂F8** show good pellets in comparisons Aspirin other batches. P.S.D data of all batches are shown in table 1.

The current interest shown in **novel drug delivery systems (NDDS)** and the pioneering research to devise new strategies for effective delivery of drugs in the body or the fine tuning of the existing technologies to enhance their efficiency. Several strategies are being tried out currently to discover novel carriers for the drugs to be delivered inquisitively and effectively. Novel drug

delivery system refers to the use of a delivery device with the objective of releasing at a predetermined rate, or at specific time or with an autonomous release profile, at a desired area of effect. The NDDS essentially efforts are now being made to devise carriers that can clairvoyant multiple drugs and release them on command.

CONCLUSION:

In epilogue, the multi unit particular tablet of Aspirin (AS₂F8) prepared using Eudragit RS and Eudragit L in a ratio 85:15 in 9% seems to be marvelous tailor-made and further in vivo study may be carried out. The next step in the process of investigating how MCC affects the drug release of Product is to analyze the results from the full dosage study that was abandoned in this report. This was because the results could squandering time, since the laboratory that performed the analysis had too complications and could not prioritize the full dosage samples. The results from these samples will however be exquisite to analyze since the same punch was used throughout the manufacturing. This will lead to less annulment in the results, compared to the results in this study that have some fallaciousness due to the usage of different punches.

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